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Uluslararası Sosyal, Siyasal ve Mali Araştırmalar Kongresi

International Congress of Social, Political and Financial Researches

IV. USSMAK
TAM VE ÖZET METİN
BİLDİRİ KİTABI
PROCEEDINGS BOOK

13-14 MART/MARCH

2026

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Uluslararası Sosyal, Siyasal ve Mali Arařtırmalar Kongresi
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***Tam ve Özet Metin
Bildiri Kitabı / Proceedings Book***

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PLENILUNE PUBLISHING

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Yayınevi / Publisher

PLENILUNE PUBLISHING
Elektronik Materyal Baskı
Mart / 2026

ISBN

978-625-94540-5-4

Düzenleyen / Organizer

Mali Araştırmalar Derneği

Destekleyenler / Supporters

Uluslararası Sosyal, Siyasal ve Mali Araştırmalar Dergisi (USSMAD)
Bulletin of Economic Theory and Analysis (BETA)

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A Comparative Analysis of Turkey and Azerbaijan on Public Finance, Governance, and the Ethics of Tax Evasion

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ABSTRACT

This study uses data from Wave 7 of the World Values Survey to investigate opinions in Turkey and Azerbaijan regarding the morality of tax evasion. On a 10-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting that tax evasion is never justified and 10 denoting that it is always justified, respondents in both nations were asked if they believed that tax evasion could ever be justified. To find out if demographic factors are linked to differences in views, mean comparisons and p-values were calculated using Welch's t-test, both overall and by gender, age, income level, and education level. The results indicate that the Azerbaijan sample is far less opposed to tax evasion than the Turkey sample, despite the fact that both populations express considerable hostility to it (with mean scores below 3 in both countries). According to within-country comparisons, income level shows a roughly linear pattern in both countries, with higher income being linked to greater acceptance of tax evasion, though there is no significant difference between the two highest income groups in Azerbaijan. Gender and education level are also not significant demographic variables in either country, and age is only significant for the 30–49 versus 50+ comparison in Azerbaijan. These findings are examined in the context of the larger body of research on the morality of tax evasion as well as the political, historical, and cultural ties between Turkey and Azerbaijan.

Keywords: *Tax evasion, Tax morale, World Values Survey, Public Finance, Governance*

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